

PECULIARITIES OF THERMAL MEASUREMENTS UNDER QUASI-ADIABATIC LOADING OF ARAMID - PLASTIC SHELLS

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SUMMARY: Results of investigations of heat emission/absorption processes in aramid-plastic shells made by a helical-circumferential winding subjected by internal hydrostatic pressure are presented in the report. The temperature change in the liquid during pressure increase and construction features of a thermal-receiver due to insufficient thermal stabilization of cool soldering, were studied. Problems of heat conductivity for thermal receiver, accounting for its weak thermal stabilization, and for a shell wall, influence of liquid heating under pressure, were solved. Thermal kinetic curves corresponding to polymeric shell at its deformation were obtained on the base of solutions of heat conductivity problems. The dependencies obtained were analyzed from viewpoint of physical processes accompanying a deforming of shells. An endothermic process is observed in the elastic area of shell deforming. This result is confirmed by theoretical calculation of heat effect for the shells considered. The results agree with experimental data obtained by acoustic method.

KEYWORDS: non-destructive method, aramid-plastic, shell, heat, temperature, pressure, heat conductivity.

INTRODUCTION

Deformation process of composite materials is a thermodynamic one. From the experimental viewpoint it implies that determination of mechanical characteristics must be supplemented by simultaneous measurements of temperature or heat changes. The thermal effects accompanying deformation process, are usually insignificant and their measurement presents the basic difficulty for transition from mechanical to thermodynamic description of the deformation process. However, the use of such measurements is obviously important and perspective for study of polymers and composite materials on their basis. It is connected with microheterogeneity of polymers caused by areas with various types of elasticity. Besides, the large range of morphological changes under deformation is inevitably accompanied by energy transformations.

Method of a measuring of heat effects accompanying a deformation of composites may be considered as one of non-destructive methods of their properties control. Besides, an information obtained may be applied for properties diagnostics, for example, load-carrying capacity. Results of investigations of heat emission/absorption processes in aramid-plastic

shells made by a helical-circumferential winding subjected by internal hydrostatic pressure are presented in this report.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The subjects of investigation were thin-walled cylindrical shells of aramid plastics with outer diameter (D) of 410 mm. These shells were made by helical-circumferential winding of aramid fibres on the base of epoxy binder. Angles of reinforcement with respect to the axis of shells were equaled to $\pm 24^\circ$ and 90° (angle α). A number of layers with specified lay-up of fibres were 6 and 13, respectively (thickness h). Thermoelectric thermometers consisting of a collection of copper-constantan thermocouples were used as sensors for measurement of heat flow. Total number of thermocouples was about 25000. Sensors were placed on a cylindrical part of the shells. Loading of the shells by internal pressure was carried out at rate of 0.8 MPa/min. Internal pressure was maintained during 5 min and then unloaded practically instantaneously. Levels of applied pressure were 2, 4 and etc up to 8 MPa. Final level of loading, where the heat measurements were carried out, was equaled to 0.6-0.7 from burst pressure. Axis and circumferential deformations, and pressure were recorded simultaneously with heat effects measurements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The time dependencies of temperature change (ΔT) under deformation directly obtained in experiment are presented in Fig.1 for one of the structures considered.

Fig.1 Time dependencies of temperature change (ΔT) of shell at loading by internal hydrostatic pressure (sections A-B), exposure of applied pressure (sections B-C) and reset of pressure (sections C-D). Figures 20, 40, 60 and 80 corresponds to levels of applied pressure of 2 MPa, 4 MPa, 6 MPa and 8 MPa.

Loadings were carried out up to 2, 4, 6 and 8 MPa. Endo-thermal process is observed at initial stage of the construction loading by internal pressure. The heat, absorbed during the loading,

is released at unloading. Let's note, that calorimetric researches of unidirectional aramid plastic under deformation along reinforcement direction showed, that the exothermic effect is observed during its deformation. To understand physical processes accompanying loading of structures with complex reinforcement scheme, the theoretical calculation of adiabatic change of structure temperature was carried out under its loading. It was necessary to know reinforcement scheme of the composite and operating stresses. The dependencies for membrane cylindrical layered shells and data [2, 3] were used for calculation of the stress-strain state of the structures [1]. The choice of such design model is proved by axisymmetric loading of the construction and carried out on the base of the theory of thin-walled shells. The cylindrical shell with the bottoms was considered. Effective thermal-elastic properties were calculated by means of the theory of layered shells, taking into account the orientation of layers in the package (90^0 , $\pm 24^0$). The stresses and deformations in the layers in axes of symmetry for each layer were calculated by means of effective stresses and deformations of the package. The thermal effect was estimated on the basis of the calculated stresses (Table 1) and characteristics of a structures (Table 2) under shell loading:

$$\Delta T = \sum_{i=1}^3 \varphi_i (\beta_L^i \cdot \Delta \sigma_L^i + \beta_T^i \cdot \Delta \sigma_T^i) \cdot T / (C_p \cdot \rho), \quad (1)$$

where index i corresponds to the direction of fibres in the layers 90^0 and $\pm 24^0$, $\Delta G_{L,T}$ – increment of stresses in the axes of symmetry (L - in longitudinal direction, T - in transverse direction), φ_i - relative thickness of a layer, $\beta_{L,T}$ - coefficient of linear thermal expansion, T - temperature, ρ - density C_p - heat capacity. It was determined, that endothermic process occurs in elastic area of shells deforming. The calculation results obtained are agreed with experimental data.

Table 1. Calculated values of normal stress $\sigma_{L,T}$ and strains $\varepsilon_{L,T}$, shear stress τ_{LT} and strain γ_{LT} in layers of a cylindrical part of constructions of two types at the level of internal pressure 2 MPa

Type	layer angle α	φ_i	ε_L $\times 10^2$	ε_T $\times 10^3$	γ_{LT} $\times 10^3$	σ_L , MPa	σ_T , MPa	τ_{LT} , MPa
1	90	2/6	0.512	1.074	3.0	393	11.3	6.3
	± 24	4/6	0.174	4.450		139	20.3	
2	90	5/13	0.262	0.779	1.37	201	6.72	2.9
	± 24	8/13	0.108	2.320		86	10.8	

Table 2. The characteristics unidirectional aramid plastics and geometrical sizes of structure

E_L , GPa	E_T , GPa	$\nu_{T,L}$	$D/2$, m	$h \times 10^3$, m	$\beta_L \times 10^6$, 1/K	$\beta_T \times 10^6$, 1/K	C_p , J/(kgK)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$, kg/m ³
76	4	0.34	0.2	2.4-4.7	- 2.1	64	1150	1.35

It is found that the heat flow recorded at shell loading depends upon two heat processes. Their sources a deformed layered shell and a liquid inside the shell creating internal pressure. Step by step analysis of system "loading liquid – organic-plastic shell – thermal-receiver" was carried out to take into account the influences effected on recorded changes of shell temperature. The temperature change in the liquid during pressure increase and construction features of a thermal-receiver due to insufficient thermal stabilization of cool soldering, were studied. Problems of heat conductivity for thermal receiver, accounting for its weak thermal

stabilization, and for a shell wall, accounting for influence of liquid heating under pressure, were solved.

The first stage of the work consists of the solution of the thermal conductivity equation for the separate thermocouple (copper-constantan), which was modeled by a core:

$$\partial u / \partial t = a^2 \partial^2 u / \partial x^2 + R (u - \Theta), \quad (2)$$

with boundary conditions:

$$u|_{x=0} = f(t), \quad \partial u / \partial x|_{x=l} = 0, \quad u|_{t=0} = \Theta,$$

where x - coordinate along a core, $u(x, t)$ - temperature, Θ - initial temperature, t - time, l - length of a core, $a^2 = k / (C_p \rho)$, k - thermal conductivity, C_p - heat capacity, ρ - density, $f(t)$ - searched function of temperature of a construction surface. The air surrounded the core was considered as a media with small thermal conductivity ($R \approx 0$).

As a result of solution of the equation (2) obtained by method of decomposition Fourier, analytical expression was received for the difference of temperatures between seals of the thermocouple depending on time is derived:

$$\Delta u(t) = 4/\pi \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [(-1)^{n+1}/(2n-1)] \exp(-\lambda_n t) [\lambda_n \int_0^t f(\zeta) \exp(-\lambda_n \zeta) d\zeta - \exp(-\lambda_n t) f(t) + \Theta], \quad (3)$$

where $\lambda_n = [\pi a(2n-1)/2l]^2$ - eigenvalues of a spectral problem. The function of surface temperature was represented as follows:

$$f(t) = \sum_{m=1}^N A_m \sin(m\omega t), \quad (4)$$

where $\omega = \pi / 1000$, N - quantity of parameters to be minimize.

For the account of influence heating under pressure an equation of thermal conductivity for a wall of the shell is composed:

$$\partial u / \partial t = a^2 \partial^2 u / \partial x^2 + g(t) \quad (5)$$

with boundary conditions:

$$u|_{x=0} = \psi(t), \quad \partial u / \partial x|_{x=s} = 0, \quad u|_{t=0} = \Theta,$$

where x - coordinate along the thickness of the sell wall, $u(x, t)$ - temperature of the wall, Θ - initial temperature of system, $\psi(t) = \Theta \exp(\beta_{fl} P(t) / C_{fl} \rho_{fl})$ - temperature of a liquid, β_{fl} , C_{fl} , ρ_{fl} - coefficient of thermal expansion, heat capacity and density of a liquid, respectively, $p(t)$ - pressure, t - time, s - wall thickness, $a^2 = k_w / (C_w \rho_w)$, k_w - thermal conductivity along coordinate x , C_w - heat capacity, ρ_w - density of aramid plastic, $g(t)$ - searched function of thermal power of the wall of a construction.

As a result of the solution of the equation (5) by method of decomposition Fourier, analytical expression was received for temperature of external surface of a construction with thermal power function of a wall and temperature of a liquid inside:

$$u(t)|_{x=s} = 4/\pi \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [(-1)^{n+1}/(2n-1)] \exp(-\lambda_n t) [\lambda_n \int_0^t \psi(\zeta) \exp(-\lambda_n \zeta) d\zeta - \exp(-\lambda_n t) \psi(t) + \Theta +$$

$$+ \int_0^t g(\zeta) \exp(-\lambda_n t) d\zeta] + \psi(t), \quad (6)$$

where $\lambda_n = [\pi a(2n-1)/2s]^2$ - eigenvalues of a spectral task. The function of thermal power of a wall was represented as:

$$g(t) = \sum_{m=1}^N B_m \sin(m\omega t), \quad (7)$$

where $\omega = \pi / 1000$, N – quantity of parameters for minimization.

The amplitudes B_m were calculated by means of method of the least squares, substituting (7) in (6) and minimizing (6), taking into temperature of surface $f(t)$ earlier determined. It allowed to determine $\Delta T(t)$:

$$\Delta T(t) = \int_0^t g(\zeta) d\zeta \quad (8)$$

and calculate temperature dependencies of the itself construction under loading (Fig.2).

Fig.2: **a** - time dependencies of temperature change (ΔT) of shell loaded by internal hydrostatic pressure (P) to levels of applied pressures of 2 MPa (T_{20}), 4 MPa (T_{40}), 6 MPa (T_{60}) and 8 MPa (T_{80}). Points, denoted by (\bullet), correspond to the pressures, which were held constant during $t = 30$ sec.; **b** - time dependencies of internal hydrostatic pressure (P).

An endothermic process is observed in the elastic area of shell deforming. Generation of damages in the material was accompanied with exothermic process. The results obtained agree with experimental data by acoustic method (Fig. 3).

Fig.3 Time dependencies of temperature change (ΔT) and speeds of increase of pulses of acoustic issue (\dot{N}) of shell loaded by internal hydrostatic pressure to levels of applied pressures of of 6 MPa (T_{60}) and 8 MPa (T_{80}).

CONCLUSION

The considered methodical features of the thermal method allows us to decide the problem of adequate description of the thermal behaviour of polymeric structures at their loading by internal hydrostatic pressure. The results obtained can be used not only for the understanding of the physical processes occurring in the objects of research under deformation, but also as variables of the state for diagnostics of their operational properties.

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